

Solar Powered Membrane Bioreactors – A Promising Technology for Water Reuse in East Africa

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Abstract

Membrane bioreactor (MBR) technology has attracted great attention over the past three decades and has experienced rapid growth in an increasing number of practical small- and large-scale applications worldwide. However, its application in Sub-Saharan Africa has been limited. The installation and operation of solar powered pilot membrane bioreactors (MBR) in Kisumu (Kenya) and Kampala (Uganda) takes an integrated approach by providing an integrated, sustainable, cost-effective, and robust solution for water treatment and reuse that also meets the demand for clean water for a variety of applications as a promising example of the water-energy nexus approach.

Introduction

Membrane bioreactor (MBR) technology is a combination of the conventional activated sludge process and micro- and/or ultrafiltration. It has attracted great attention in the last three decades and has achieved rapid growth in an increasing number of practical small- and large-scale applications worldwide. The main advantages of MBR application include high effluent quality (for water reuse), small footprint and complete separation of hydraulic retention time (HRT) and solids retention time (SRT). However, its application in Sub-Saharan Africa has been limited. Very few MBRs installed in Africa were mainly imported as costly units from developed countries and they are not well suited for local application.

Materials and Methods

This paper presents results from two operational pilot plants in Kenya and Uganda. The installation and operation of a pilot MBR in Kisumu (Kenya) was studied within the EU funded project VicInAqua. It takes an integrated approach by providing an integrated, sustainable, cost-effective, and robust solution for water sanitation that also meets the demand for clean water in the fish processing industry,

aquaculture, and irrigation (Gukelberger et al., 2020). Another MBR plant to treat the wastewater has been installed at a hospital in Kampala, Uganda to treat wastewater and provide water for reuse in applications such as toilet flushing or irrigation. The Reuse4Hos project (www.reuse4hos.de) was funded by the funding organisation German Federal Environmental Foundation (Deutsche Bundesstiftung Umwelt, DBU).

Results and Discussion

The MBR installed in Kenya treated wastewater (3-4 m³/day) was used to replenish water losses in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) for tilapia fingerling rearing without any adverse effects. The semi-autonomous energy system consisting of a 14.3 kWp photovoltaic (PV) system and a 30 kWh lithium battery storage was installed to ensure maximum system security despite the frequent power outages. Approximately 40 % degree of autonomy has been achieved. The scalable pilot plant can be adapted to all local fish species and will contribute to sustainable fish production and job creation in the local fish industry. Fig. 1 shows the water quality results for two different modules (commercial module and a newly developed low fouling module). These results show particularly a high COD and ammonium removal. Especially ammonium is a critical parameter for fish in aquaculture due to its toxicity.

The MBR installed in Uganda has a capacity to produce about 7 – 8 m³/day of treated water. The unit was installed using mainly locally available components (tanks, pumps, aerators etc.). A granular activated carbon (GAC) filter was installed downstream in order to remove pharmaceutical residues / micropollutants. The pilot plant was powered by 20 PV modules with a total power of 7 kWp. A 3.55 kWh supercapacitor battery provided uninterrupted power supply during day and can also provide some power at night in case of a power outage. Surplus energy is stored in the battery or fed into the hospital's grid.

Fig. 1 Water parameters of the pilot MBR providing treated domestic wastewater for aquaculture and irrigation (Gukelberger et al., 2020)

Conclusions

Based on the promising results of two small-scale solar-powered MBR pilot plants in Kenya and Uganda a new upscaled solar powered MBR is a logical next step. Therefore, within the recently launched EU project PrAectiCe a new larger MBR (production capacity of 20-25 m³/day of treated water) will be designed and installed at the existing VicInAqua pilot site in Kisumu (Kenya) in order to provide clean water for the expansion of the aquaculture production.

References

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